

Stress-Test Execution Log

Project: AxionQECC

Purpose: Provenance artifact for results reported in AxionQECC_Full_Paper_v4

Notes: Raw, unedited console output. No post-processing applied.

```
PS C:\Dev\AxionC_BD\PowerShell-7.5.3> cd C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle
```

```
PS C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle> cd C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle
```

```
>> python run_phase2_sweep.py --project_dir . --matrix phase2_matrix.json --max_jobs 10
```

```
>>
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\run_phase2_sweep.py:6: SyntaxWarning: invalid escape sequence '\q'  
python run_phase2_sweep.py --project_dir C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle --matrix phase2_matrix.json  
[phase2] combos=100 seeds=5 total_runs=500
```

```
[run]
```

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py  
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --  
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --  
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0
```

```
{  
  "episodes": 400,  
  "num_arms": 44,  
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0"  
}
```

```
TTF summary: {'tff': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,  
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

```
[run]
```

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py  
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --  
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --  
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1
```

```
{  
  "episodes": 400,  
  "num_arms": 44,  
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1"  
}
```

```
TTF summary: {'tff': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,  
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

```
[run]
```

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py  
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --  
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --  
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2
```

```

{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
}

```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py

```

--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[phase2] reached max_jobs=10; stopping early.
PS C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle> python run_phase2_sweep.py --project_dir . --matrix
phase2_matrix.json
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\run_phase2_sweep.py:6: SyntaxWarning: invalid escape sequence '\q'
  python run_phase2_sweep.py --project_dir C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle --matrix phase2_matrix.json
[phase2] combos=100 seeds=5 total_runs=500
[skip] rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0 (ttf_summary.json exists)
[skip] rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1 (ttf_summary.json exists)
[skip] rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2 (ttf_summary.json exists)
[skip] rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3 (ttf_summary.json exists)
[skip] rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4 (ttf_summary.json exists)
[skip] rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0 (ttf_summary.json exists)
[skip] rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1 (ttf_summary.json exists)
[skip] rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2 (ttf_summary.json exists)
[skip] rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3 (ttf_summary.json exists)
[skip] rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4 (ttf_summary.json exists)
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1
{
  "episodes": 400,

```

```
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2
{
"episodes": 400,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3
{
"episodes": 400,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4
{
"episodes": 400,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

```
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
```

```

safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
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}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":

```

```
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
```

ython.exe

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0
```

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
```

ython.exe

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1
```

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
```

ython.exe

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2
```

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
```

ython.exe

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3
```

```

{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
}

```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py

```

--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3
{
  "episodes": 400,

```

```
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
"episodes": 400,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p6_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0
{
"episodes": 400,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1
{
"episodes": 400,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

```
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
```

```
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
}
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
}
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
}
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

```

ython.exe

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2
```

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3
```

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4
```

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0
```

```

{
  "episodes": 400,
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}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
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[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2
{
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  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3
{
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  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
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}

```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4

```
{
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  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
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"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
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"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py

```

--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
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}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4
{
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  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0
{
  "episodes": 400,

```

```
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1
{
"episodes": 400,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2
{
"episodes": 400,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3
{
"episodes": 400,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

```

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --

```

```
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
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[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
}
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
}
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
}
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
```

ython.exe

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4
```

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p6_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0
```

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1
```

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2
```

```

{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
}

```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py

```

--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2
{
  "episodes": 400,

```

```
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3
{
"episodes": 400,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4
{
"episodes": 400,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0
{
"episodes": 400,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

```
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
```

```
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.6 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p6_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
}
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
}
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
}
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

```

ython.exe

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1
```

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2
```

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3
```

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4
```

```

{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}

```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py

```

--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3
{
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  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
  "episodes": 400,

```

```
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0
{
"episodes": 400,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1
{
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}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2
{
"episodes": 400,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

```

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --

```

```
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3
{
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  "out_dir":
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}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
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  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1
{
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"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
```

ython.exe

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3
```

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
```

ython.exe

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4
```

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
```

ython.exe

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0
```

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
```

ython.exe

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1
```

```

{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}

```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0

```
{
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  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py

```

--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
}
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
}
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
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[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
}
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1
{
  "episodes": 400,

```

```
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2
{
"episodes": 400,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3
{
"episodes": 400,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
"episodes": 400,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

```
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1
{
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"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
```

```
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
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[run]
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C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
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[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2
{
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  "out_dir":
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}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
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[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
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[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
```

ython.exe

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0
```

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1
```

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
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```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2
```

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3
```

```

{
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  "num_arms": 44,
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}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
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[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
}

```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
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"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
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"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py

```

--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1
{
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}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2
{
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  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
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[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3
{
  "episodes": 400,

```

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"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
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[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4
{
"episodes": 400,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0
{
"episodes": 400,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1
{
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"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
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```

```

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2
{
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  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --

```

```
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1
{
  "episodes": 400,
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"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
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}
TTF summary: {'tff': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
```

ython.exe

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2
```

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3
```

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4
```

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0
```

```

{
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"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1
{
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  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
}

```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py

```

--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0
{
  "episodes": 399,

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"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
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}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 14, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 13, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1
{
"episodes": 399,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 3, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 2, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2
{
"episodes": 399,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 13, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 12, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3
{
"episodes": 399,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 3, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 2, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

```
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 15, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 14, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 3, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 2, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 3, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 2, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
```

```
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 3, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 2, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 4, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 3, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 3, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 2, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 3, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 2, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 3, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 2, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 3, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 2, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 4, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 3, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
```

ython.exe

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4
```

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 3, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 2, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0
```

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 4, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 3, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1
```

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 6, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 5, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2
```

```

{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 3, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 2, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 3, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 2, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 3, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 2, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
}

```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 10, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 9, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 3, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 2, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 5, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 4, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 16, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 15, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py

```

--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 5, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 4, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 10, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 9, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 5, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 4, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2
{
  "episodes": 399,

```

```
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 5, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 4, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3
{
"episodes": 399,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 18, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 17, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
"episodes": 399,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 2, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 1, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0
{
"episodes": 399,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 10, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 9, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

```
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 5, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 4, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 5, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 4, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 18, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 17, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
```

```
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 2, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 1, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 10, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 9, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 5, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 4, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 5, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 4, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 18, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 17, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 5, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 4, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 3, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 2, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
```

ython.exe

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1
```

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 2, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 1, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2
```

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 3, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 2, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3
```

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 6, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 5, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4
```

```

{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 2, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 1, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 2, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 1, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 2, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 1, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
}

```

TTF summary: {'tff': 3, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 2, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'tff': 2, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 1, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'tff': 12, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 11, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'tff': 2, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 1, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py

```

--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 2, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 1, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 3, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 2, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 2, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 1, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4
{
  "episodes": 399,

```

```
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 12, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 11, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0
{
"episodes": 399,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 10, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 9, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1
{
"episodes": 399,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 25, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 24, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2
{
"episodes": 399,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 20, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 19, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

```

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 17, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 16, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 33, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 32, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 2, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 1, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --

```

```
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 8, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 7, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 5, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 4, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 10, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 9, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 14, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 13, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 2, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 1, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 8, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 7, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 4, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 3, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
```

ython.exe

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3
```

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 13, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 12, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4
```

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 4, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 3, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0
```

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 2, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 1, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1
```

```

{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 8, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 7, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 4, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 3, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 13, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 12, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
}

```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 4, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 3, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 23, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 22, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 19, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 18, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 20, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 19, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py

```

--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 20, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 19, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 21, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 20, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 2, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 1, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1
{
  "episodes": 399,

```

```
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 13, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 12, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2
{
"episodes": 399,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 5, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 4, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3
{
"episodes": 399,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 11, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 10, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4
{
"episodes": 399,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 14, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 13, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

```

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 4, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 3, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 4, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 3, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 5, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 4, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --

```

```
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 9, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 8, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 4, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 3, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 4, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 3, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 4, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 3, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 5, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 4, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 9, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 8, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 4, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 3, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
```

ython.exe

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0
```

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 27, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 26, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1
```

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 32, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 31, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2
```

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 25, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 24, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3
```

```

{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 9, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 8, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p9_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 33, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 32, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 13, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 12, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
}

```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 11, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 10, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2"

}

TTF summary: {'ttf': 14, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 13, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3"

}

TTF summary: {'ttf': 12, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 11, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4"

}

TTF summary: {'ttf': 13, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 12, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py

```

--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 13, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 12, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 11, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 10, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 11, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 10, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3
{
  "episodes": 399,

```

```
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 11, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 10, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
"episodes": 399,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 11, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 10, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0
{
"episodes": 399,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 13, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 12, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1
{
"episodes": 399,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 11, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 10, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

```
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 11, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 10, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 11, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 10, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 11, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 10, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
```

```
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0
{
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  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 12, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 11, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
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}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 11, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 10, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
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C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2
{
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}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 12, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 11, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
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C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 11, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 10, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 11, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 10, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
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[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
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C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 8, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 7, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 9, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 8, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
```

ython.exe

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2
```

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
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  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p98_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 9, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 8, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3
```

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p98_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 11, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 10, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4
```

```
{
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  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p98_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 9, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 8, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
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```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0
```

```

{
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}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 8, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 7, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1
{
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  "num_arms": 44,
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}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 9, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 8, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
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ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2
{
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TTF summary: {'ttf': 9, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 8, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
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[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3
{
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}

```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 9, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 8, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4

```
{
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  "out_dir":
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"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4"

}

TTF summary: {'ttf': 9, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 8, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0

```
{
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  "out_dir":
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"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0"

}

TTF summary: {'ttf': 8, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 7, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1

```
{
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  "out_dir":
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"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1"

}

TTF summary: {'ttf': 9, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 8, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py

```

--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 9, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 8, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 9, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 8, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
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C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
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}
TTF summary: {'tff': 9, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 8, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0
{
  "episodes": 399,

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"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p98_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 8, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 7, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1
{
"episodes": 399,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p98_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 9, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 8, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2
{
"episodes": 399,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p98_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 9, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 8, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3
{
"episodes": 399,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p98_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 9, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 8, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

```
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 9, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 8, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

```
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 8, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 7, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

```
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1
{
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  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 6, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 5, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

```
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
```

```
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 8, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 7, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
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}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 7, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 6, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4
{
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}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 8, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 7, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0
{
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  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 6, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 5, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
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[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1
{
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  "num_arms": 44,
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}
TTF summary: {'tff': 5, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 4, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 7, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 6, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3
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  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 7, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 6, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
```

ython.exe

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4
```

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p98_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 8, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 7, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0
```

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p98_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 6, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 5, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1
```

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p98_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 5, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 4, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2
```

```

{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p98_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 7, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 6, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p98_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 7, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 6, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p98_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 8, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 7, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p98_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
}

```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 6, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 5, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 10, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 9, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 8, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 7, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 7, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 6, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py

```

--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 8, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 7, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 6, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 5, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 5, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 4, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2
{
  "episodes": 399,

```

```
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 5, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 4, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3
{
"episodes": 399,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 5, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 4, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4
{
"episodes": 399,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 5, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 4, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0
{
"episodes": 399,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 7, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 6, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

```
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 5, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 4, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 4, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 3, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 6, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 5, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
```

```
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 5, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 4, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 7, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 6, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 5, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 4, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 4, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 3, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 6, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 5, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 5, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 4, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 7, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 6, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
```

ython.exe

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1
```

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 5, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 4, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2
```

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 6, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 5, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3
```

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 6, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 5, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4
```

```

{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 6, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 5, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 3, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 2, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 4, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 3, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}

```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 3, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 2, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3"

}

TTF summary: {'ttf': 3, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 2, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4"

}

TTF summary: {'ttf': 4, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 3, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
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"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0"

}

TTF summary: {'ttf': 3, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 2, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py

```

--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 4, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 3, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 3, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 2, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 4, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 3, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
  "episodes": 399,

```

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"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 3, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 2, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0
{
"episodes": 399,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 3, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 2, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1
{
"episodes": 399,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 4, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 3, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2
{
"episodes": 399,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 3, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 2, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

```
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 4, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 3, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 3, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 2, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 5, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 4, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
```

```

safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 8, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 7, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 5, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 4, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 5, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 4, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.98 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":

```

```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p98_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 7, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 6, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
}
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
}
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
}
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

```

ython.exe

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3
```

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4
```

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0
```

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1
```

```

{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}

```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py

```

--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1
{
  "episodes": 400,

```

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"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2
{
"episodes": 400,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3
{
"episodes": 400,
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"out_dir":
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}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
"episodes": 400,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

```

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --

```

```
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
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[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
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}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
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}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
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[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
```

ython.exe

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0
```

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1
```

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2
```

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3
```

```

{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'tff': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
}

```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 1.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale1p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py

```

--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3
{
  "episodes": 400,

```

```
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4
{
"episodes": 400,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0
{
"episodes": 400,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
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C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1
{
"episodes": 400,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

```

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --

```

```
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
```

ython.exe

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2
```

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
```

ython.exe

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3
```

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
```

ython.exe

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4
```

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale2p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
```

ython.exe

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0
```

```

{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
}

```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py

```

--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0
{
  "episodes": 400,

```

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"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1
{
"episodes": 400,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2
{
"episodes": 400,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3
{
"episodes": 400,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

```

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --

```

```
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 2.5 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale2p5_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifffix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
```

ython.exe

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4
```

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0
```

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s0"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 41, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 40, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1
```

```
{
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  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s1"
```

```
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 15, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 14, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max':
0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

[run]

```
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2
```

```

{
  "episodes": 400,
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"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
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C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s3
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
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}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
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[run]
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ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
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}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
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[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s0
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
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}

```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 41, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 40, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1

```
{
  "episodes": 399,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s1"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 15, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 14, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s2"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py --episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 3 --out

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3

```
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
```

"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s3"

```
}
```

TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}

[run]

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py

```

--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4
{
  "episodes": 400,
  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p01_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 0 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s0
{
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  "num_arms": 44,
  "out_dir":
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}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s1
{
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  "num_arms": 44,
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}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2
{
  "episodes": 400,

```

```

"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s2"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 3 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3
{
"episodes": 400,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s3"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 1.0 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho1p0_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4
{
"episodes": 400,
"num_arms": 44,
"out_dir":
"C:\\qecc_push_bundles\\qecc_push_v6_bundle\\out_phase2\\rho1p0_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
}
TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3,
'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
[phase2] done. ran=490
PS C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle> TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None,
'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400,
'terminal_penalty_note': None}
ParserError:
Line |
    1 | TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, â€¦
      | ~
      | Unexpected token ':' in expression or statement.
PS C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle> [run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.8 --noise_scale 3.0 --leak_scale 2.0 --p_leak 0.02 --seed 4 --out

```

C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4

ParserError:

```
Line |
  1 | [run] C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoft
```

```
~
| Unexpected token
```

'C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe' in expression or statement.

```
PS C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle> {
```

```
>> "episodes": 400,
```

```
>> "num_arms": 44,
```

```
>> "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p8_noise_scale3p0_leak_scale2p0_p_leak0p02_s4"
```

```
>> }
```

ParserError:

```
Line |
  2 | "episodes": 400,
```

```
~
| Unexpected token ':' in expression or statement.
```

```
PS C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle> TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400, 'terminal_penalty_note': None}
```

ParserError:

```
Line |
  1 | TTF summary: {'ttf': 400, 'absorbed': False, 'absorb_episode': None, 
```

```
~
| Unexpected token ':' in expression or statement.
```

```
PS C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle> [run]
```

C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_drifftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 0 --out
```

```
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0
```

ParserError:

```
Line |
  1 | [run] C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoft
```

```
~
| Unexpected token
```

'C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\python.exe' in expression or statement.

```
PS C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle> {
```

```
>> "episodes": 399,
```

```
>> "num_arms": 44,
```

```
>> "out_dir":
```

```
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s0"
```

```
>> }
```

ParserError:

```
Line |
  2 | "episodes": 399,
```

```
~
```

```

| Unexpected token ':' in expression or statement.
PS C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle> TTF summary: {'ttf': 14, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 13,
'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400,
'terminal_penalty_note': None}
ParserError:
Line |
  1 | TTF summary: {'ttf': 14, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 13, 'absor
    |
    | ~
    | Unexpected token ':' in expression or statement.
PS C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle> [run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 1 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1
ParserError:
Line |
  1 | [run] C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoft
    | ~~~~~
    | Unexpected token
    |
'C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe' in expression or statement.
PS C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle> {
>> "episodes": 399,
>> "num_arms": 44,
>> "out_dir":
"C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s1"
>> }
ParserError:
Line |
  2 | "episodes": 399,
    | ~
    | Unexpected token ':' in expression or statement.
PS C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle> TTF summary: {'ttf': 3, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 2,
'absorb_consec': 2, 'absorb_fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_max': 0.3, 'fail_tol': 0.25, 'episodes_requested': 400,
'terminal_penalty_note': None}
ParserError:
Line |
  1 | TTF summary: {'ttf': 3, 'absorbed': True, 'absorb_episode': 2, 'absor
    |
    | ~
    | Unexpected token ':' in expression or statement.
PS C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle> [run]
C:\Users\TechGod\AppData\Local\Microsoft\WindowsApps\PythonSoftwareFoundation.Python.3.12_qbz5n2kfra8p0\p
ython.exe
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\qecc_epoch_contextual_bandit_v12_track4A_soft_noise_fsm_driftfix.py
--episodes 400 --d 5 --T 8 --drift --add_emergency_arm --use_emergency_override --override_k 3 --override_ctx_hi 7 --
override_fail_hi 0.36 --use_regime_gating --gate_ctx_hi 6 --gate_fail_hi 0.3 --safe_repump_period 1 --
safe_repump_success 0.7 --rho 0.9 --noise_scale 1.0 --leak_scale 1.0 --p_leak 0.01 --seed 2 --out
C:\qecc_push_bundles\qecc_push_v6_bundle\out_phase2\rho0p9_noise_scale1p0_leak_scale1p0_p_leak0p01_s2

```